

STRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES OF CARBON NANOTUBE REINFORCED COMPOSITE FIBRILS

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ABSTRACT

Recent studies showed that on the molecular level, carbon nanotubes (CNT) possess many unique characteristics that promise to revolutionize the world of structural materials resulting in significant impact on our capability to build lighter, smaller and higher performance structures for aerospace, electronic packaging and many other industrial applications. When the CNT are aligned, micromechanical studies showed an order of magnitude increase in mechanical properties comparing to the state of the art carbon fiber reinforced composites..

In order to realize the exciting potential of CNT, there is a need for processing methodologies and robust manufacturing technology to convert the CNT to macroscopic structures. To assure the proper transfer of the properties of CNT to the structural level, an integrated design for manufacturing methodology reflecting the hierarchical structural geometry must be available. The co-electrospinning process is introduced as a means to align and carry the CNT in the form of nanocomposite fibrils; thus forming the precursor for linear, planar and 3D textile assemblies for macrocomposites.

Accordingly it is the objective of this paper to introduce a concept that converts CNT into nano scale super composite fibrils (SCF) by the co-electrospinning process. Using these SCF as building blocks, a framework for hierarchical design for manufacturing will be presented along with analytical and experimental results. In order to develop an understanding of the structure and property relation of the nanocomposite fibrils, our study have been focused on the molecular level, composite fibril level and fibril assembly level. The structural, compositional and physical properties of the carbonized and non-carbonized CNT/PAN fibrils were characterized by transmission electron microscope (TEM), Raman spectroscopy, and Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM).

Keywords: carbon nanotubes, nanocomposites, carbon nanofibrils, electrospinning, super composite fibrils (SCF)

INTRODUCTION

With a tensile modulus of over 1 TPa, tensile strength of well over 30 GPa, and breaking elongation of 6 % or higher,[1] carbon nanotubes (CNT) promise to be an important basic building block for a new class of engineering materials that will have far reaching impact on the next generation of advanced composite products ranging from aerospace vehicles, to surgical implants, to micro and nanoelectronic components. Although tremendous progress has been made in the synthesis and characterization of SWNT[2-4] a major challenge remains in the search for an effective means to bridge the dimensional and property gap between nanotubes and

engineering materials and structures.[3-7] In order to translate the superior properties of CNT to meso and macro scale structures, considerable effort has been devoted to the development of linear and planar CNT assemblies.[8-10] We report herein a continuous process capable of carrying single-wall nanotubes (SWNT) in a continuous nanoscale composite fibril that can be used in a variety of composites. Alignment of SWNT bundles in the composite fibril has been successfully achieved by the electrospinning process through flow and charge induced orientation as well as the confinement effect. Upon heat treatment, the composite fibrils are carbonized at 1100°C to form the SWNT/carbon yarns. SWNT structure has been maintained after carbonization. This process provides a convenient means to assess the fundamental question of fiber diameter effect and it has a potential to produce the next generation of advanced carbon fibers for reinforcement of composites.

THE CO-ELECTROSPINNING PROCESS

Electrospinning is an electrostatic induced self-assembly process capable of producing ultra-fine fibers down to the nanoscale [11,12]. In the electrospinning process, a high voltage electric field is generated between an oppositely charged polymer fluid contained in a polymer reservoir with a capillary tip and a metallic fiber collector for randomly oriented or aligned nanoscale fibrils as shown in Figures 1. By electrospinning of a combination of CNT and polymer solution, the co-electrospinning process has created exciting processing options for multifunctional composite materials [13].

To demonstrate our co-electrospinning concept, polyacrylonitrile (PAN) from Scientific polymer product SP² Catalog # 134 with weight average molecular weight of 150,000 was used for the carbon fiber precursor. The CNT used in this study are single walled carbon nanotubes produced at Rice University via the HiPCO method [14]. All material used in the studies described here was produced in HiPco experimental run HPR92 (lasting from July 19 to July 24, 2001). This raw material contained approximately 24% Fe catalyst by mass, so material was purified using a protocol similar to that previously reported [15,16] by placing the raw CNT in a convection oven held at 225 degrees Celsius for 16 hours. During this time, a slow flow of water-saturated air was passed through the oven. The material was then placed in concentrated HCl and stirred at room temperature for one day. Following this, the nanotube/acid slurry was diluted with HPLC grade water and transferred to a buchner funnel assembly. A peristaltic pump supplied a slow drip of water to the slurry which was washed for three days, at which time the effluent from the nanotube cake was measured to be pH 7.0. The material was then transferred in wet paste form into sealed bottles for later electrospinning studies.

Various proportion of the purified carbon nanotubes(CNT) ranging from 1 to 5 % by weight in relation to the PAN polymer were dispersed in the DMF by sonication. The PAN polymer in powder form were dissolved in the DMF/CNT mixture to form a 7% by weight of PAN solution. Electrospinning was carried out under ambient temperature in a vertical spinning configuration using a 0.9 mm diameter glass pipette with a spinning distance of 15 cm driven a voltage of 25 KV. An aluminum foil ground collector was used to collect the electrospun fibers. Heat treatment of the electrospun CNT/PAN nanofibrils was carried out by first stabilizing the fibrils at 200°C in Oxygen environment for 30 minutes. Upon cooling in air the fibrils were carbonized by heating to 750°C in nitrogen environment for 1 hour. The carbonized CNT/PAN fibril were then graphitization at 1100°C for 1 hour in nitrogen environment.

It was showed in our laboratory that the purified single wall carbon nanotube (CNT) can be co-electrospun with polyacrylonitrile (and other polymers) to form carbon nanotube composite fibrils and yarns (CNY) By subsequent heat treatment it was demonstrated, as shown in Figure 2., that

CNT can be aligned and attenuated to composite fibrils as fine as 5 nm by the co-electrospinning process. Figure 3 show the CNT yarn spun by the co-electrospinning process prior to heat treatment. These CNT/PAN nanocomposite fibrils in green form or in carbonized and graphitized form will serve as the super reinforcement in linear, planar and 3-D preform for a new generation of composites and fibrous assemblies.

Figure 1. Co-electrospinning of CNT

Figure 1a. Random nanofibrils

Figure 1b. Aligned nanofibrils

Figure 2. TEM micrograph showing first evidence of alignment of CNT during the electrospinning process.

Figure 3a. The CNY manufacturing process

Figure

3b. Continuous CNT yarn

STRUCTURES OF CNT/PAN COMPOSITES

Compositional, structural, and physical characterization of the carbon nanotube nanocomposite fibrils confirmed the capability of the co-electrospinning process to align and orient CNT in a polyacrylonitrile (PAN) matrix.

The successful inclusion of oriented CNT in the PAN matrix fibril was demonstrated using Raman spectroscopy analysis as shown in Figure 4. The typical peak of CNT (100-275 cm^{-1} and 1500-1600 cm^{-1} range) can be seen in the CNT/PAN fibrils and not in the PAN fibrils. The diameter of the SWNTs was estimated from the RBM peaks by the diameter-frequency relationship: $\omega_R \sim 224 \text{ cm}^{-1} \cdot \text{nm} / d$, where ω_R is the RBM frequency and d is the tube diameter [17,18]. The presence of at least 6 RBM peaks is observed in the range from 130-275 cm^{-1} in Fig. 4, which, according to the above equation, corresponds to a tube diameter range from 0.8 nm to 1.7 nm.

Figure 4. Raman Spectra of (a) PAN and (b) CNT/PAN Fibrils

The orientation of CNT in the PAN composite fibril is further confirmed by high resolution transmission electron microscope (HRTEM) observation showing good alignment of CNT along the fibril axis. (Figure 5.) The surface topological information of the nanocomposite fibrils was obtained by Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM). As shown in Figure 6, a smooth surface was detected for the pristine PAN nanofibril whereas the CNT /PAN nanocomposite fibril is characterized by a rough, cobble stone-like surface morphology.

Figure 5. High-resolution TEM (HRTEM) micrograph showing a uniform distribution, no agglomeration and excellent CNT alignment in a PAN fiber with the diameter of about 50 nm. Such distribution of nanotubes is expected to be achieved in other electrospun polymer/CNT systems and maintained after carbonization.

Figure 6. AFM images of (a) PAN fiber; (b) CNT/PAN Fiber showing agglomeration.

THERMAL STABILITY OF CNT/PAN COMPOSITES

The CNT contents in the PAN nanofibers can be detected by the thermogravimetry (TGA) method. Both pure PAN and CNT/PAN nanofibers were heated in the air atmosphere at a rate of 20°C/min. As shown in Figure 7, decomposition of PAN takes place at 308°C for the pure PAN nanofiber and 325°C for the CNT/PAN nanofiber, indicating that CNT in the PAN nanofibers increases PAN's thermal stability. The difference of the remaining weight between these two samples (56.8% for pure PAN and 61.2% for CNT/PAN) at the plateau region (around 330°C) is due to the CNT contents in the CNT/PAN nanofibers. Assuming that the same decomposition mechanism for these two samples, the CNT content in the CNT/PAN can therefore be calculated to be 10 wt %. The results suggest that 10% of CNT in the CNT/PAN nanofibers increases the decomposition temperature of PAN nanofibers by 17°C.

Figure 7. TGA analysis of PAN (dotted line) and CNT/PAN (solid line) nanofibers in air.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CNT/PAN COMPOSITES

Initial experiments were carried out using a transverse compression load deformation test by the cantilever deflection method (Figure 8a). A nonlinear load-deformation relationship for the CNT/PAN composite nanofibril is shown in Figure 8c illustrating a higher resistance to deformation with the addition of CNT. The elastic modulus of the fiber was evaluated and calculated based on the approach of Kracke and Damaschke [19]. The method utilizes the relationship $dF/d(\Delta z) = (2\Delta^{1/2})E^*A^{1/2}$, where A is the contact area, E^* is the effective Young's modulus of the contact as defined by: $1/E^* = (1-\nu_1^2)/E_1 + (1-\nu_2^2)/E_2$. Here, E_1 , E_2 and ν_1 and ν_2 are the elastic moduli and the Poisson's ratios of the sample and the tip. Using the results shown in Figures 8(b) and 8(c) the modulus of the CNT/PAN and PAN fibers were calculated.

Figure 8. (a) Schematic for elasticity measurement. (b) Cantilever deflection vs. sample height in a cycle of compression and relaxation. (c) Load vs. indentation curves

In Figure 9, a plot of the modulus as a function of the weight fraction and volume fraction of the CNT in the PAN matrix is shown. A comparison of the modulus predicted by the rule of mixture (ROM) assuming a CNT modulus of 1 TPa, show an unusual departure from the ROM prediction indicating a factor of greater than “2” of the CNT effect.

Figure 9. Modulus-Volume fraction relation of CNT Nanocomposite Fibril

Summary

Convincing experimental evidence showed that composite polymer and carbon nanofibrils containing aligned CNT can be manufactured by the co-electrospinning process. Continuous yarns have been successfully fabricated using this process with encouraging thermal and mechanical properties demonstrating the capability of CNT contributes to thermal stability and a significant reinforcement effect with only less than 3% by volume of CNT content. When the process is optimized and the engineering properties of nanocomposite fibrils and the CNT yarns are fully characterized, these CNT yarns will serve as an effective means to deliver CNT in linear, planar and 3-D forms which will undoubtedly lead to many functions and applications.

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